

Review of concepts for Construction and Demolition Waste and the Circular Economy

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Abstract: In order for construction and demolition waste (CDW) volumes, recovery targets and associated calculation rules to be quantified more accurately, it is critical that the types of CDW are classified and that the domains of the various ways in which it is managed are specified. This forms the foundation for formulation policies aimed at managing waste, as well as the implementation of regulatory measures designed for environmental protection. Globally, numerous guidelines, policies and regulations have emphasised CDW as a result of the significant volumes generated on an annual basis. Nevertheless, ambiguity regarding the definition of CDW coupled with a lack of clarity in terms of the breadth of methods employed for managing waste creates considerable challenges for the effective management of this type of waste. Furthermore, although the concept of the circular economy (CE) in the construction sector has attracted the attention of scholars, governments, and organisations, it appears to be merely an amalgamation of disparate and unstructured ideas. While the general perception is that transitioning to a CE facilitates a reduction in the demand for natural resources, this idea remains specious and unclear. Hence, the aim of this paper is to critically understand how CDW is classified, as well as to differentiate between the various methods employed in the waste management process. Additionally, it presents a discussion on the existing thought regarding the concept of CE in the context of the construction sector. The paper's findings can inform practical measures aimed at enhancing waste management application in addition to the ramifications for CE by offering guidance for planning, decision-making and establishing targets for reducing and recovering waste.

Keywords: construction and demolition waste, construction and demolition waste management, circular economy, concept.

1. Introduction

Construction and demolition waste (CDW) accounts for more than one third of total waste in the European Union and is generated across the entire lifecycle of a building. Numerous countries have placed particular emphasis on CDW in their policies for managing waste, as well as the implementation of regulatory measures for environmental protection. Nevertheless, CDW classification and the progressive innovation and development of methods used for waste management introduce new concepts which make this procedure complex, unclear and difficult to understand, which presents considerable challenges for managing CDW adequately. These problems mean that waste volumes and treatments are not accurately identified and there is a lack of clarity regarding the breadth of application of recovery targets along with their calculation rules. Moreover, the concept of the circular economy (CE) has attracted the attention of scholars, governments, industry and other organisations, particularly within the construction sector. This is a result of its considerable promise in facilitating sustainable development. Nonetheless, research on this concept remains superficial, lacks clarity and appears to be an amalgamation of disparate ideas. In this paper, CDW classification will be explored, the domain of the various methods employed for managing this waste will be evaluated, and the existing thought regarding the concept of CE in the context of the construction sector will be discussed. A review of concepts will be provided which can help understand current and future practices in CDW management.

2. The concept of Construction and demolition waste (CDW)

There are several definitions for CDW. One common definition, as published by the European Environmental Agency, is “Rubble and other waste material arising from the construction, demolition, renovation or reconstruction of buildings or parts thereof, whether on the surface or underground. Consists mainly of building material and soil, including excavated soil. Includes waste from all origins and from all economic activity sectors” (EEA 2017). Other environmental institutions have used more generic definitions of CDW, such as DEFRA who stated that CDW is “a waste stream that is primarily received from construction sites” (DEFRA 2015), and EPA who defined CDW as “debris generated during the construction, renovation and demolition of buildings, roads, and bridges” (EPA 2023). In any case, these definitions comprise hazardous and non-hazardous materials, which difference is defined in Art 3.2 of the Waste Framework Directive (EC, 2018). On the other hand, inert waste is considered as ‘waste that does not undergo any significant physical, chemical or biological transformations and is unlikely to adversely affect other matter which it comes into contact’ (Environment Agency, 2020). Mineral waste (such as concrete or bricks) is normally considered as inert, but gypsum, although classified as non-hazardous waste, it is banned in landfills in some countries and regions.

Globally, different attempts have been made to classify the types of CDW. The most recognised classification is issued by the European waste catalogue (EWC) (EC, 2014) as shown in table 1. Chapter 17 of this EWC comprises the majority of waste that is produced in construction, renovation, and demolition sites. For waste to be managed precisely, it is of

significant importance that the types of CDW are clearly classified so that management policies can be formulated and monitored and the processing of associated departments can be coordinated. If CDW is classified in a practical manner, this will facilitate a uniform understanding, which is advantageous for the communication and coordination of all relevant parties, quantifying of waste, reporting and optimisation of resource use.

Table 1: CDW classification according the ECW (EC, 2014)

CDW Classification (chapter 17)	Code
- Concrete, bricks, tiles and ceramics	17.01
- Wood, glass and plastic	17.02
- Bituminous mixtures, coal tar and tarred products	17.03
- Metals (including their alloys)	17.04
- Soil (including excavated soil from contaminated sites), stones and dredging spoil	17.05
- Insulation materials and asbestos-containing construction materials	17.06
- Gypsum-based construction material	17.08
- Other construction and demolition wastes (waste containing mercury and PCB, mixed waste and dangerous materials)	17.09

3. The concept of construction and demolition waste (CDW) management

During the entire life of a building, varying types and volumes of waste are generated, including the processes of manufacturing, construction, renovation, and demolition. Nevertheless, CDW do not include waste produced during manufacturing processes even though CDW is often incorporated as part of their supply chain, and it is expected this flow to grow together with CDW recovery policies in the following years. This is because manufacturing and construction have different production system characteristics, as their taxonomies and regulations differ (EWC 2014). On the other hand, there are manufacturing byproducts (term defined by the Waste Framework Directive) which are used as materials in construction. That is the case of, for example, fly ash from coal energy plants or sawdust from saw mills.

Comprehending the different ways in which waste can be effectively managed is critical for successfully transitioning to a circular economy within the construction sector (Figure 1). According to the Waste Framework Directive, waste management is defined as ‘the collection, transport, recovery (including sorting), and disposal of waste, including the supervision of such operations and the aftercare of disposal sites, and including actions taken as a dealer or broker’ (Directive 2018/851). Nevertheless, the idea of waste management is targeted at the promotion of methods for treating waste, with a particular focus on the prepare for reuse and recycling rather than energy recovery and disposal activities in line with the guidelines on the waste hierarchy.

The Waste Framework Directive defines this waste hierarchy, but additional concepts are being proposed to be added, following the concept of circular economy (CE) and zero waste

targets. In the construction industry, we identify aspects such as maintenance, repair, remanufacture, refurbishing, adaptability, deconstruction/disassembly, etc. The consideration of these concepts during the design stage will save the large majority of avoidable waste in the whole life cycle of a built asset. This is what is called as 'design out waste' (CLC, 2020).

Figure 1. Waste hierarchy (EC, 2008)

The process of sorting CDW is critical for preparing waste to be recovered and safely disposed. It is always advised to do on site whenever possible as it will facilitate the waste management process and the later transportation and classification at the waste treatment plant.

One of the main ways in which CDW is minimised is through the preparation of waste for reuse. This is where construction products with reuse potential are checked, cleaned and, with small repairs, be ready for use again. One of the prerequisites for an item to be 'prepared for reuse' is that it was waste before, while 'reuse' occurs when the original product safety and quality are not compromised after initial use (Directive 2008/98/EC). For example, it is possible for residual products to be reused on different sites for the identical purpose for which they were originally designed with no need for them to be pre-processed. Second-hand, repaired or remanufactured elements can substitute virgin or new equivalents as well, but it involves further processes with the manufacturer's involvement, which is understood as 'reverse logistics'.

But the concept of waste is not achieved if it is reused in the same construction site, whereas it will become waste if it is reused in another different site, in which case it should be treated accordingly. This is a legal aspect that tries to promote reuse in the same place where waste can be produced.

Figure 1: Waste management methods throughout the building lifecycle

Waste recycling is where waste is reprocessed into products, substances, or materials with a similar or different purpose as the original one. Therefore, secondary materials can be utilised as a replacement or in conjunction with virgin materials. It is critical that the different CDW types are properly characterised so that the plethora of opportunities available can be exploited. Nevertheless, misconceptions exist regarding what can be categorised as recycling operations (Directive 2008/98/EC). Some examples are as follows:

- Energy recovery involves the conversion of the organic fraction of CDW into a form of energy that can be used (EEA 2017). Nonetheless, this is considered as an end-of-pipe method, therefore outside the concept of circular economy, and with detrimental environmental effects.
- Backfilling is defined as ‘any recovery operation where suitable non-hazardous waste is used for purposes of reclamation in excavated areas or for engineering purposes in landscaping’. This absorbs large volumes of construction waste, and grows waste recovery rates artificially (In the UK, more than 75% of construction waste recovery in 2011 was backfilling (EC, 2019)). It is a good solution for excavation waste, but not for CDW when higher values could be achieved if it is properly recycled. In several occasions, backfilling is just an excuse for not managing CDW correctly.
- Landfilling demand for CDW is large and provides a good solution for excavation waste. Despite that, it must be recognised that a similar situation happens as with backfilling. A commonly used approach for CDW disposal involves the use of landfills for residual waste that remains after treatment processes have been applied.

4. Circular economy and CDW management

There is a misconception that CE is the same as ‘waste management’ or ‘recycling’ and the concepts are often mixed up. CE refers to the retention of value across the entire supply chain of a product, structure, or service lifecycle (Figure 2). Although there is no consensus regarding how CE is defined, it is largely perceived that transitioning to CE results in zero waste generation and a reduction in demand of natural resources. According to the definition proposed by the ARUP, CE is an economy ‘where the value of products, materials and resources is maintained in the economy for as long as possible, and the generation of waste minimised’ (European Commission 2015). From the perspective of the OECD, the objective of CE is to ‘transform the current linear economy into a circular model to reduce consumption of finite material resources by recovering materials from waste streams for recycling or reuse, using products for a longer time and exploiting the potential of the sharing and services economy’ (Yamaguchi 2021). As suggested by the aforementioned definitions, CE denotes a transition towards sustainable development. through waste minimisation, ensuring that natural resources maintain their value to the greatest extent possible, and decoupling economic expansion from the detrimental effects of depleting resources and environmental deterioration.

Figure 2: CE flow map

Transitioning to CE necessitates the adoption of three primary mechanisms, namely: narrowing resource loops, slowing loops, and closing resource loops (Ginga et al. 2020):

- For material flows to be narrowed, natural resources must be used more efficiently such as by adopting more effective technologies in the construction process.

- For material flows to be slowed, the materials' usage stage must be increased, generally by enhancing the durability of the built asset (maintenance, repair, etc.).
- Lastly, closing material loops requires secondary materials, as well as products that have been repaired or manufactured. The closed-loop mechanism is the primary approach to create an effective framework in terms of preparation for use and waste recycling (Ellen MacArthur Foundation 2013).

5. Conclusion

In order for CDW to be effectively managed and to transition successfully to a circular economy, it is critical to understand how waste is classified and the scope of methods employed for managing waste. Erroneous perceptions and ambiguities surrounding these concepts can have a negative effect on planning and decision-making in addition to the establishment of waste recovery goals. This paper re-explores the literature in order to examine how CDW is classified, along with an evaluation of the domain of the various methods of managing waste and a discussion on the existing thought on the concept of CE with respect to the construction sector.

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